

**IMPROVEMENT THE QUALITY OF TRAINING OF
PROFESSIONAL SPECIALISTS BY USING ELECTRONIC
EDUCATIONAL RESOURCES**

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Abstract. *This article substantiates the approach to the use of electronic educational resources as a tool for developing new forms and methods of self-development of students' professional knowledge and skills, expressed in the form of methodological guidelines and adapted for the implementation of the educational process within the framework of modern pedagogical technologies and other teaching systems. The main goal of informatization of the education sector at the present stage is to obtain new knowledge, master new methods of their assimilation, all-round development of cognitive interests, information needs, and creative potential of students.*

Keywords: *quality of education, information educational environments, electronic educational resources, new forms and methods of self-education, individual learning paths.*

Introduction

Cardinal changes in the political and economic arrangement of society, the formation of a new worldview ideology and morality, qualitative changes in the content of the internal state of the subjects of the educational environment and forms of subject-subject relations, the activation of informatization processes in modern conditions became factors in the necessity for fundamental transformations in the

educational sphere. Under the influence of these factors, formed different changes in existing and fundamentally new approaches to the practice of implementing educational activities in educational institutions (EI). In order for the perception of these approaches and technologies not only to bring new knowledge to students, but also to be the best in form and productive in terms of the content of educational didactic content, we need to fill them with new content.

Main part

Since one of the most important properties of the modern educational environment is its informational nature, students' best perceive information and communication technologies (ICT) that implement various forms and methods of teaching in information educational environments (IEE). Together with traditional object-oriented educational technologies, ICT should provide:

- creation of electronic educational resources (EER);
- implementation of the perception and reproduction of the content of the EER by using appropriate interactive tools;
- operational information exchange, direct and feedback active systems within the educational process.

The methodology of learning and self-learning in information environments involves the development of technologies and forms of information presentation related to the implementation of the educational process. At the same time, any modern pedagogical technology (MPT) involves the implementation by the teacher of a certain set of organizational measures carried out within the framework of teaching methods and self-learning in information environments [5].

Readiness for learning and self-learning implies that the trainees have a number of skills and abilities, namely:

- independently organize, manage, regulate their educational activities, as well as determine the most promising ways of its development;
- correctly identify their interests and needs, abilities and opportunities within the framework of the potential of the intellectual development of the individual.

The task of the IEE is to develop these and other skills and abilities of students, as well as to fill them with the information content of didactic content, providing:

- identification and conceptual (semantic, aspect) interpretation of terms;
- formation of professional knowledge and ideas about the content of the relevant specialties;
- assimilation of universal values in the learning process;
- formation of motivation for learning and the need for self-learning based on the implementation of interpersonal interaction in accordance with these values.

Today it is obvious to everyone that the conditions for vocational education are diverse. Therefore, it is quite difficult to balance the system of logically clear requirements for it. However, in the latest edition of the Federal State Educational Standards (FSSES) its authors made an attempt to balance the financial, economic,

personnel, educational, educational and methodological, as well as information requirements for the IEE and its structure. In accordance with the requirements specified in the Federal State Educational Standard, each educational institution creates its own educational programs, which provide for the mandatory presence of target, content and organizational components, as well as a system for assessing the level of knowledge of students. Thus, the Federal State Educational Standard determines the special importance of IEE in modern education, which, on the one hand, is the area for the implementation of educational interactions, and on the other hand, an integrated information resource for the practical implementation of the educational process [1]. Therefore, IEE is not just an information educational environment, or an educational environment expressed in informational form, but its representation (image, projection) in information tools, resources, technologies, teaching and control systems, expressed in the form of methodological guidelines and adapted for implementation of educational process [5].

When using traditional methods and means of subject teaching (textbook, workshop, and visual aids), the rate of assimilation of didactic content depends mainly on the average properties of the contingent of students. With the active use of the potential of IEE (its resources and technologies), the rate of assimilation of didactic content largely depends on the individual characteristics of each student and increases due to the efficiency of the implementation of links between him as a subject of learning and IEE resources. This circumstance determined by the fact that the IEE resource, as a standard information product, has the means of adapting its state and functioning in accordance with the individual needs and personal characteristics of the learning subject using it. This increases the possibility of variability and individualization of the process of subject education, in particular, the choice by the trainee (if desired) of an individual learning path.

The usage of MPT in the educational process allows you to increase the level of knowledge and the quality of professional self-development of students. Among the MPTs implemented within the framework of the IEE, it is customary to include training in small groups, thematic discussions, situational analysis, business games, the project method, the formation of a “trainee portfolio”. For the organization and conduct of each of them, modern EERs actively used [2].

В малых группах можно лучше организовать совместную деятельность обучаемых, учитывая из разные уровни познавательной деятельности для достижения общей цели на основе принципов взаимовыгодного сотрудничества (collaborating learning, cooperative learning). Usually small groups (no more than 5-6 students) formed by the teacher, taking into account their individual abilities, wishes and psychological compatibility.

With this approach to the formation of groups, we can ensure that there are trainees with different abilities in one group who, during the learning process, will be able to provide each other with the necessary assistance.

Thematic discussion as one of the forms of MPT also has a problem, which requires its resolution. This form refers to effective methods of persuasion, since in the process of its implementation; all students independently come to unambiguous conclusions. At the same time, participation in a discussion is fundamentally different from communication at a seminar and is rather a complex intellectual process, and not just answers to questions. The thematic discussion usually based on the free expression of one's own position and its reasoned defense.

A more complex method of problem-based learning is situational analysis, since it combines elements of a business game and thematic discussions. As a rule, situational analysis designed to develop the necessary theoretical knowledge and skills in trainees, as well as the ability to apply them in practice. For the practical solution of a problem situation, a special web page is usually used; if possible, feedback organized through chatting or videoconferencing.

The usage of educational role-playing and business games of a problem orientation within the framework of ISE allows us to find possible ways to solve the problem through a set of specific plots. At the same time, if a business game aimed at developing the necessary professional qualities, then in a role-playing game, abilities and skills developed that are not necessarily associated with a particular profession. The advantage of conducting role-playing games is the simulation of not only real, but also fictional situations.

One of the popular informational teaching aids in recent years has become the project method, which we can consider as a way to achieve didactic learning goals through a detailed development of the problem, which should end with a very real practical result, formalized in the form of its specific solution [3]. The practical implementation of the project method provides for the active development of research and search activities of students and involves the usage of discussions, brainstorming, as well as role-playing and business games to solve the problem.

Modern IEE involves the expansion of the practice of introducing various kinds of telecommunication projects that allow organizing joint educational, cognitive, research and creative activities of students within the framework of the project. At the same time, the activities of all participants in such a project aimed at solving a common problem and achieving a joint result. It has one goal, a set of agreed methods and ways to solve it. Typically, the sequence of actions when organizing a project in practice can be as follows:

- 1) definition of the subject of the project and the number of its participants;
- 2) definition of the main problem of the project;
- 3) formation of a set of assumptions and hypotheses for further research of the project problem and their distribution by groups of trainees;
- 4) appointment of persons responsible for solving individual tasks within small groups of trainees;
- 5) individual study of trainees within the framework of the project, aimed at finding a solution to the main problem;

6) exchange of received data, opinions and other useful information in order to form intermediate versions of the solution to the main problem;

7) discussion of intermediate versions of the solution of the main problem with the project coordinator;

8) protection of versions of the solution of the main problem developed by separate groups in the form of presentations, discussions, reports, and so on, on a forum or in a videoconference format;

9) comprehensive analysis of the work done and the formulation of conclusions based on its results.

The participation of students in joint project activities contributes to the formation of many useful skills in them, for example, such as: conducting a discussion, searching for the necessary information, the ability to analyze it, the ability to draw conclusions based on generalizations, conduct experimental research, etc.

Another form of MPT aimed at improving the quality of professional self-development of trainees is the formation of a “portfolio”. Its meaning is to encourage students to positive self-assessment of the level of their knowledge, which is especially important in the process of learning and self-learning [4]. MPT “Portfolio of trainees” involves the formation of a set of such skills as an objective assessment of the results achieved, objective determination of the main reasons for success or failure, correct identification of ways to eliminate shortcomings and errors, an objective attitude to external evaluations of other people.

The organization of work on this technology provides the creation for each student of his own web page, on which he can form his “portfolio”.

Approaches to its creation can be very different, the main thing is that trainees receive the necessary skills to analyze their work, their own successes and failures, and be able to assess the level of their knowledge.

The filling of the “portfolio of trainees” occurs as they complete various tasks, creative works or projects, as well as current tests. As a result, at the end of the course, each student has his own “portfolio”, based on which any teacher or an independent expert commission can assess the final level of his knowledge, skills, skills formed because of independent work.

Orientation towards obtaining new educational results using MPT and EER entails significant changes not only in the activities of educational institutions, but also in the implementation of a new pedagogical system of education through the formation of the structure and content of the IEE. Under these conditions, the task of developing the necessary skills for organizing independent cognitive and practical activities in students to improve the quality of professional self-development becomes more relevant [6].

The main goal of informatization of education is not only the assimilation of new knowledge, but also the mastery of ways and methods to achieve it, the com-

prehensive development of cognitive interests, information needs, and the creative potential of students.

To achieve learning outcomes and develop the motivational resources of students, it is necessary to switch to a personality-oriented educational process based on individual educational programs developed taking into account the personal potential, capabilities and interests of students.

Conclusion

To improve the quality of professional self-development of students in modern conditions, it is necessary that the educational process does not “adjust” to the available EER and MPT, but allows students to choose the resources they need. Therefore, the IEE of a modern educational institution forms as an integrated multicomponent system that combines in its composition not only the components of educational and research activities, but also the components of monitoring and assessing the level of knowledge of students. At the same time, the IEE should be as varied as possible and provide all its possible users with differentiated MPT and EER in the required volume.

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